

Sustainable Leadership: A Review of Recent Trend

¹**Marini Purwanto*, Business Faculty of Catholic Widya Mandala University , East Java/Surabaya, Indonesian

²**Lena Ellitan*, Business Faculty of Catholic Widya Mandala University , East Java/Surabaya, Indonesian

*Correspondence: marini@ukwms.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Sustainable Leadership emerged as a new leadership paradigm in the sustainability era, starting with the issue of ethical leadership. Ethical leadership is based on social power, focusing on how leaders use social power. them in making decisions, the actions they take and the way leaders influence others in six attributes, namely character and integrity, ethical awareness, community/people orientation, motivating, encouraging and empowering and managing ethical accountability. *Sustainable Leadership* is a new paradigm in sustainable leadership which is defined as sustainability regarding the creation of current and future profits for an organization while improving the lives of all parties (JT McCann & Holt, 2010) . *Sustainable Leadership* emerged as a concept that considers the idea of *the Triple Butoon Line perspective* (Elkington, 1997) which focuses on organizational leadership that balances *people, planet, profit* for a sustainable future. This paper explains the concept of sustainable leadership as a new paradigm that leaders need to respond to global challenges in the era of sustainability, reviews how the history of the birth of the concept of sustainable leadership was initiated by the idea of ethical leadership and developed into a new concept in the field of leadership that is strongly oriented towards various stakeholders. and a track record of ongoing leadership research in both developed countries and developing countries. First concept from ethical leadership, the concept of sustainable leadership has developed into a new concept in the field of leadership that synergizes with servant leadership and transformational leadership . The existence of synergy between leadership styles answers a leadership development challenge to look beyond the boundaries of the organization's needs internal and see from the external aspects of the organization and accommodate the needs of future generations. Sustainable leadership has implications for a value-based leadership development model and strategic decision-making that takes into account economic, social and ecological dimensions so that organizations have prosocial, as well as pro-nature, behavior. This sustainable leadership paradigm provides opportunities for future research related to sustainable leadership development that is focused on sustainability issues.

Keywords: Sustainable leadership, values-based leadership, strategic decision making, sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The philosophical idea that humans should ideally protect the earth, namely coexistence and harmony between humans and nature, is the goal of 193 United Nations countries that have agreed to 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs). Various literature has examined when and how the concept of *Sustainable Leadership* emerged, starting from the concept of sustainable development in the field of organizational management which was first introduced by the Brundtland committee (Brundtland, 1987) where the concept of sustainable development is a way of development to meet current needs without sacrificing the needs of future generations.

This paper will discuss the origins of the concept of *Sustainable Leadership*, first developed in educational concepts (Hargreaves & Fink, 2006) and then developed as a new paradigm in leadership practice in the sustainability era (Hargreaves, nd), (Hargreaves & Fink, 2012). In answering a theory or concept, this article will discuss the process of how the origins of this leadership practice developed until today, criticism of the concept of *sustainable leadership* compared to other leadership theories and implications for the development of value-based leadership needed for strategic decision making that ensures that the impact organizational performance towards achieving sustainability in a balance of 3 pillars of sustainable performance, namely economic, environmental and social aspects of performance. This article also discusses the direction of *sustainable leadership research* in the future, which is still open to developing the concept of *sustainable leadership*.

History of the Sustainable Leadership Paradigm

Sustainable Leadership emerged as a new leadership paradigm in the sustainability era, starting with the issue of ethical leadership, in the article (Resick et al., 2006), (Hargreaves & Fink, 2006) explains that ethical leadership is based on social power, focusing on how leaders use social power. them in making decisions, the actions they take and the way leaders influence others in six attributes, namely character and integrity, ethical awareness, community/people orientation, motivating, encouraging and empowering and managing ethical accountability. Ethical leadership involves leading by respecting the rights and dignity of other people (Ciulla, nd), because basically ethical leaders involve social power for the purpose of sustainability. Ethical leadership relates to considerate behavior, honesty, trust in leaders, interactional justice, charismatic leadership and ethical leadership exploring social learning theory (*Perspective Learning Theory*) as a theoretical basis for understanding ethical leadership (Brown et al., 2005). In qualitative research it was found that ethical leadership has values-based integrity and inspirational characteristics (Treviño et al., 2003).

Sustainable Leadership paradigm was then developed in an educational context in *the journal of education* (Hargreaves & Fink, 2006) *sustainable leadership*, Andy Hargreaves and Dean Fink discuss one of the most important and often overlooked aspects of leadership: sustainability that there are 7 interesting and original principles of sustainable leadership, characterized by deep learning and real achievement, not superficially tested performance; Duration of impact over the long term, beyond individual leaders, through effectively managed succession; (Slankis, 2006) conceptualizes the 10 pillars of *sustainable leadership* as the potential for organizations to achieve competitive advantage and direct continuous improvement that is change-oriented, systems thinking, social and environmental awareness, business intelligence and credibility, adaptability, patience, thinking skills in action, persuasiveness, energetic and passionate, mentoring and development. *Sustainable Leadership* is a new paradigm in sustainable leadership which is defined as sustainability regarding the

creation of current and future profits for an organization while improving the lives of all parties (JT McCann & Holt, 2010) . *Sustainable Leadership* emerged as a concept that considers the idea of *the Triple Bottom Line perspective* (Elkington, 1997) which focuses on organizational leadership that balances *people, planet, profit* for a sustainable future.

(Critchley, 2009) argues that *sustainable leadership* has 3 core processes, namely learning by doing, having clear personal goals, awareness of personal motivation and a state of effective management and adequate self-care. starting from the individual level then developing strategic micro level leadership in developing organizational sustainability (Suriyankietkaew & Avery, 2014) .

Sustainable leadership focuses on motivating sustainability at the individual, organizational, social and ecological levels, existing and future groups, providing implications for strategic decision making in organizational sustainability (Pearse, 2015) . *Sustainable leadership* has emerged as a new concept in overcoming sustainability challenges. SL is seen as a resource and brings opportunities to organizations for continuous improvement, innovation opportunities and sustainable competitive advantage (JT McCann & Holt, 2010) .

The sustainable leadership view is rooted in ideas that organization is part of nature. Organization _ must create sustainable, knowledge-based, value creating knowledge, and which generates income supported by social, physical, ethical and business reasons (Shrivastava 1995) in (J. McCann & Sweet, 2014) . Sustainability incorporates strategies to ensure that performance The best businesses combine concern for the environment and society (Jutras 2009).

Sustainable leadership then developed in a global context where sustainable leadership is a holistic leadership practice that balances *people, planet, profit* to support organizational resilience and sustainability (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) . *Sustainable Leadership* is an alternative leadership approach called "Rhineland" "Honey Bee" sustainable leadership. Sustainability is not just about companies being environmentally friendly and carrying out CSR. The opinion of *Sustainable Leadership* emerged because of the limitations of the shareholder-first approach in the United States:

1. French economist Michael Abert believes that the pursuit of profit is a threat to neoliberal capitalism because its short-term focus can hinder long-term thinking, investment and planning.
2. Charles Handy reminded us that the purpose of business is not just to make a profit but to achieve a higher goal.
3. Michael Porter criticizes the current model that companies must consider stakeholder interests so as to create economic value and social value

Sustainable Leadership includes humanistic aspects which include assessing people and considering companies as contributors to social welfare. According to Wareen Bennis (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) *sustainable leadership* suggests recruiting, training and employing top leaders who are effective rather than heroic, suggesting companies are financially transparent for ethical purposes. Peter Drucker suggested that managers make changes and innovations come from the organization so that extraordinary things can happen. Stephen Covey urges knowledge and involvement of company employees.

Sustainable leadership conflicts with the interests of shareholders, but the goal of *sustainable leadership* is to maintain a balance of *people, profit* and *planet* in the company's sustainability

(GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2010) . *Sustainable leadership* was developed by Avery and Bergsteiner (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) with 14 samples of European organizations whose principles were contrary to shareholder philosophy and produced 19 leadership practices then called the Rhineland and Anglo/US approaches which were then continued on 14 samples in other parts of the world which were adopt the same approach at various levels . As a result, this *sustainable leadership* approach is developing in various industries and locations from developed countries in the US, UK, Australia, Europe and Scandinavia to developing countries South Africa and Thailand.

In 2011 Avery and Bergstainer expanded the practice of *sustainable leadership* by adding 4 elements, namely: trust, innovation, staff involvement and self-management. The practice of *sustainable leadership* is divided into several levels, namely: 14 Basic Practices (Foundation Practices), 6 High Level Practices (*develop & team self-, consensual management orientation, decision-making, enabling culture, knowledge retention and sharing*). 4 Main Performance Drivers (strategic, systemic innovation, staff engagement, quality). 5 Performance Outcome indicators as a result of performance on strategy implementation, namely *brand & reputation customer satisfaction, financial performance, long-term shareholder value, long-term stakeholder value* .

Peterlin 2015 in (Douglas, nd) developed a conceptual model of sustainable leadership development, based on the theory of multiple intelligences by Howard Gardner and implementing leadership through appreciative inquiry, meaning that leaders have multiple intelligences that distinguish individual profiles and are able to develop a wide range of intelligences over the leader's life span . Sustainable leadership development through multiple intelligences is an act of learning where the expected outcome of appreciative process participants is a creative seeker of positive learning, opportunities in an active learning environment. The development of the SL Model proposes new creative ways to meet the process and content needs of sustainable leadership development as its core components.

Sustainable Leadership is a new leadership paradigm that is person-centred and resource-based and arguments suggest that organizational leadership should no longer focus on the control function, and shift its focus to dialogue and interrelated ideas between leaders and subordinates, and the development of reflective and participatory leadership (Kopp & Martinuzzi , 2013) . *Sustainable Leadership* also considers stakeholders and ensuring that sustainable working relationships can be mandatory for effective long-term organizational performance (Barr & Dowding, 2022) *Sustainable Leadership* has been developing since 2011 (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) where *Sustainable Leadership* is conceptualized as sustainable leadership that requires a long-term perspective in making decisions, encouraging systematic innovation aimed at increasing customer value, developing a skilled, loyal and highly involved workforce. and offer quality products, services and solutions.

The concept of *Sustainable Leadership* continues to be developed, based on the results of research at the oldest university in Thailand (Kantabutra & Saratun, 2013) , *Sustainable Leadership* can reflect good management practices, often low costs, improve reputation and brand. In this case, SL practice increases a fast and responsible response, is competitive and attractive to stakeholders which develops not only by maximizing profits but also by shifting business philosophy with a balance of the 3 pillars of economic, social and environmental (G. Avery, 2005), (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2010) , (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) , (Gerard et al., 2017b) . (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b)

According to (G. Avery, 2005) a company is considered sustainable when over time it meets the following criteria:

- a. The organization has strong financial performance.
- b. The organization shows capacity to meet social, economic and environmental problems.
- c. The organization is able to maintain a leadership position in the industrial market.

In Avery's study (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2010) , (G. Avery, 2005) is based on 28 case studies taken on four continents which shows that companies led by Rhineland principles tend to be more sustainable and generally perform better and are able to promote value to shareholders than Anglo/US based companies.

DISCUSSION

Sustainable Leadership Research

The initial development of *sustainable leadership* in 2005 proposed 19 SL practices and in subsequent developments (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2010) SL practices have been developed with 4 additions and rearranged with 23 SL practices in three levels, namely: 14 Basic Practices (Foundation Practices) namely: developing people continuously, amicable labor relations, long-term retention of staff, internal succession planning, valuing people, CEO and top-team leadership, ethical behavior, long-term perspective, considered organizational change, financial markets, environmental responsibility, social responsibility, stakeholder approach, strong shared vision. 6 High Level Practices (devolved & team self-, consensual management orientation, decision-making, enabling culture. knowledge retention and sharing). Key Performance Drivers (strategic, systemic innovation, staff engagement, quality).

A previous bibliometric review (Suriyankietkaew & Petison, 2020) regarding the *Sustainable Leadership* framework emphasized that sustainable leadership is a management system, long-term vision and broader goals that connect organizations with society, ethical behavior, social responsibility, the environment, innovation capacity, systemic change and orientation to stakeholders. These values underlie the vision that leaders and stakeholders want to achieve through organizational sustainability and resilience (Suriyankietkaew et al., 2022) .Previous research related to Sustainable Leadership practices was mostly carried out in countries (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) , (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011a) and most *sustainable leadership practices* were carried out in large companies and were listed on the stock market (Kantabutra & Avery, 2011) (Kantabutra & Avery, 2013) . Previous research suggests more case study research in the future in different industrial contexts (Kantabutra & Suriyankietkaew, 2013) .

Criticism of Sustainable Leadership

There are many leadership style theories that have become very strong theories, but SL is still very limited in support from established scientific research, (Burawat, 2019) , (Iqbal, Ahmad, & Halim, 2020) . Several studies combine transformational leadership and SL as a combination that has an impact on sustainability performance (Burawat, 2019) . Researchers (Burawat, 2019) argue that there is potential for overlap between two or more other leadership styles and sustainable leadership. Previous research identified a relationship between servant leadership and sustainable leadership (JT McCann & Holt, 2010) .Sustainable leadership is still not at the level of a mature theoretical concept and according to an analysis by Reichers and Scheider (in Gurr, 2007), in (Pearse, 2015) they conclude that there is a difference in the focus of transformational leadership and *sustainable leadership* , where *transformational leadership*

focuses more on individual charisma and provide an impact on subordinates, while *sustainable leadership* focuses on motivating *sustainable values* at the personal, organizational, social and ecological levels for the current and future generations. However, *transformational leadership* and *sustainable leadership* have the same ideas in dedication to all stakeholder demands, stakeholder intellectuals, motivation to inspire and individual treatment of stakeholders.

Sustainable leadership on the concept of ideas (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2010) , (GC Avery & Bergsteiner, 2011b) SL focuses more on the needs of other people than the needs of the leader. However, *Servent leadership* is different from *Sustainable leadership* which focuses on future needs for all stakeholders. Leaders who have a serving and sustainable approach tend to make strategic decisions that consider sustainability performance achievements in the 3 dimensions of economic, social and ecological, but a focus on *sustainable leadership* contributes to strategic decision making by ensuring long-term effects of decisions that have a positive impact on various stakeholders. interests (Pearse, 2015) .

Implications of Sustainable Leadership in developing value-based leadership and strategic decision making

Sustainable leadership has a strong tendency towards a stakeholder-oriented approach (Iqbal, Ahmad, & Li, 2021) , so a leader with a focus on sustainability will make maximum efforts to achieve performance in a broader scope to achieve the SDGs sustainable development goals. *Sustainable leadership* is a type of leadership that complements other types of leadership such as *sustainable leadership* , *transformational leadership* , so that *sustainable leadership* can be said to be the leadership development needed in organizational strategic decisions to achieve organizational sustainability. *Sustainable leadership* focuses on resource development so that *sustainable leadership* has implications for leadership development by designing holistic programs in training programs in terms of strengthening internal aspects in developing organizational processes and considering stakeholders in improving the internal environment, coherent and cohesive values and full consideration of stakeholders (Gerard et al., 2017a) .

Sustainable leadership approach is a new paradigm in responding to the movement of change towards sustainable development where (McCauley et al., 2010) notes that the paradigm shift from leadership to collective goals, strategic actions, such as strategic decision making is reflected by top management in accordance with *Upper Echelons Theory* (Hambrick & Mason, 1984) that strategic decisions are based on top management's reflection of the leader's personal interpretation, experience and preferences. Research (Kafetzopoulos & Gotzamani, 2022) conceptualizes the influence of leadership on *sustainable performance* , where *upper echelons theory* can explain the influence of leadership on organizational outcomes , strategy selection and performance levels.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICSTION

Conclusion

This paper has identified and clarified the origins and understanding of the concept of *sustainable leadership* , but there is no one approach that can be applied in all contexts. Developing the operationalization of *sustainable leadership* is an opportunity in different contexts in future research directions and areas by developing diverse theories according to the direction and context of the research to be developed. *Sustainable leadership has implications for leadership development in the sustainability era, so that the direction of sustainable leadership development can continue to be developed in strategic decision making, sustainable*

organizations, as well as development-based leadership development and the development of integrative thinking.

Future Research Directions

Implications for future research on *sustainable leadership* need to consider cultural factors as an important aspect in the successful implementation of *sustainable leadership* (Kantabutra, 2011) . The role and development of employees and leaders must be the focus and center of success in moving towards organizational sustainability (Suriyankietkaew & Avery, 2016) , (Suriyankietkaew, 2019a) , (Suriyankietkaew, 2019b) , (Iqbal, Ahmad, & Halim, 2020) , (Iqbal, Ahmad, Nasim, et al., 2020) , (Iqbal, Ahmad, & Halim, 2021) , (Burawat, 2019) .

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by This research is part of research funded by the National Competitive Research for Beginner Lecturers, Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia in 2023, based on Decree Number 0536/E5/PG.02.00/2023 dated 30 May 2023 and Agreement/Contract Number 003/SP2H get Research Budget for the Role of Sustainability Leadership in Implementing SDGs: Green Innovation Strategy (GIS): A Review of Strategic Transformation in Organizational Sustainability.

REFERENCES

- Avery, G. (2005). *Leadership for sustainable futures: Achieving success in a competitive world* . Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Avery, G. C., & Bergsteiner, H. (2010). *Honeybees & locusts: The business case for sustainable leadership* . Allen & Unwin.
- Avery, G. C., & Bergsteiner, H. (2011a). How BMW successfully practices sustainable leadership principles. *Strategy & Leadership* , 39 (6), 11–18.
- Avery, G. C., & Bergsteiner, H. (2011b). Sustainable leadership practices for enhancing business resilience and performance. *Strategy & Leadership* , 39 (3), 5–15.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/10878571111128766>
- Barr, J., & Dowding, L. (2022). *Leadership in health care* . Sage.
- Brown, M. E., Treviño, L. K., & Harrison, D. A. (2005). *Ethical leadership: A social learning perspective for construct development and testing* . 97 , 117–134.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2005.03.002>
- Brundtland, G. H. (1987). Our common future—Call for action. *Environmental Conservation. Tetrahedron Letters* , 14 (4), 291.
- Burawat, P. (2019). The relationships among transformational leadership, sustainable leadership, lean manufacturing and sustainability performance in Thai SMEs manufacturing industry. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management* , 36 (6), 1014–1036. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-09-2017-0178>
- Ciulla, JB (nd). *WH AT IS GOOD LEADERSHIP?*
- Critchley, B. (2009). *Sustainable leadership: Perennial philosophy* .
- Douglas, E. (nd). *No Title* .
- Elkington, J. (1997). The triple bottom line. *Environmental Management: Readings and Cases* , 2 , 49–66.
- Gerard, L., McMillan, J., & D'Annunzio-Green, N. (2017a). 4 sustainable leadership. *Industrial and Commercial Training* , 49 (3), 116–126. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ICT-12-2016-0079>
- Gerard, L., McMillan, J., & D'Annunzio-Green, N. (2017b). Conceptualizing sustainable

- leadership. *Industrial and Commercial Training* , 49 (3), 116–126.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/ICT-12-2016-0079>
- Hambrick, & Mason. (1984). Upper Echelons: of Reflection of Its Organization as reflection of its Top managers. *Management* , 9 (2), 193–206. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/258434>
- Hargreaves, A. (nd). *Welcome to Sustainable leadership Susta ina b le de ve lo p me nt Sustainable development , democracy .* 1–77.
- Hargreaves, A., & Fink, D. (2006). Redistributed Leadership for Sustainable Professional Learning Communities. *Journal of School Leadership* , 16 (5), 550–565.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/105268460601600507>
- Hargreaves, A., & Fink, D. (2012). *Sustainable leadership* . John Wiley & Sons.
- Iqbal, Q., Ahmad, NH, & Halim, HA (2020). How Does Sustainable Leadership Influence Sustainable Performance? Empirical Evidence From Selected ASEAN Countries. *SAGE Open* , 10 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020969394>
- Iqbal, Q., Ahmad, NH, & Halim, HA (2021). Insights on entrepreneurial bricolage and frugal innovation for sustainable performance. *Business Strategy and Development* , 4 (3), 237–245. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.147>
- Iqbal, Q., Ahmad, N.H., & Li, Y. (2021). Sustainable leadership in frontier Asia region: Managerial discretion and environmental innovation. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* , 13 (9), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095002>
- Iqbal, Q., Ahmad, NH, Nasim, A., & Khan, SAR (2020). A moderated-mediation analysis of psychological empowerment: Sustainable leadership and sustainable performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production* , 262 . <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121429>
- Kafetzopoulos, D., & Gotzamani, K. (2022). The effect of talent management and leadership styles on firms' sustainable performance. *European Business Review* , 34 (6), 837–857. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-07-2021-0148>
- Kantabutra, S. (2011). Sustainable leadership in a Thai healthcare services provider. *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance* , 24 (1), 67–80.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/09526861111098256>
- Kantabutra, S., & Avery, G. (2013). Sustainable leadership: Honeybee practices at a leading Asian industrial conglomerate. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration* , 5 (1), 36–56. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17574321311304521>
- Kantabutra, S., & Avery, G. C. (2011). Sustainable leadership at Siam Cement Group. *Journal of Business Strategy* , 32 (4), 32–41.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02756661111150954>
- Kantabutra, S., & Saratun, M. (2013). Sustainable leadership: Honeybee practices at Thailand's oldest university. *International Journal of Educational Management* , 27 (4), 356–376.
- Kantabutra, S., & Suriyankietkaew, S. (2013). Sustainable leadership: Rhineland practices at a Thai small enterprise. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business* , 19 (1), 77–94. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJESB.2013.054313>
- Kopp, U., & Martinuzzi, A. (2013). Teaching Sustainability Leaders in Systems Thinking. *Business Systems Review* , 2 (2), 191–215. <https://doi.org/10.7350/BSR.V10.2013>
- McCann, J., & Sweet, M. (2014). The Perceptions of Ethical and Sustainable Leadership. *Journal of Business Ethics* , 121 (3), 373–383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1704-4>
- McCann, J. T., & Holt, R. A. (2010). Servant and sustainable leadership: An analysis in the manufacturing environment. *International Journal of Management Practice* , 4 (2), 134–148. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMP.2010.033691>
- McCauley, C.D., & McCall Jr, M.W. (2014). *Using experience to develop leadership talent:*

- How organizations leverage on-the-job development* . John Wiley & Sons.
- McCauley, C. D., Van Velsor, E., & Ruderman, M. N. (2010). Introduction: Our view of leadership development. *The Center for Creative Leadership Handbook of Leadership Development* , 3 , 1–28.
- Pearse, N. (2015). *Strategic Decision Making for Organizational Sustainability : The Implications of Servant Leadership and Sustainable Leadership Approaches* . *STRATEGIC DECISION MAKING FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY : THE IMPLICATIONS OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP AND* . 17 (3).
<https://doi.org/10.15458/85451.4>
- Quinn, L., & D'amato, A. (2008). Globally responsible leadership a leading edge conversation. *CCL White Paper; Center for Creative Leadership: Greensboro, NC, USA* .
- Resick, C.J., Hanges, P.J., Dickson, M.W., & Mitchelson, J.K. (2006). *A Cross-Cultural Examination of the Endorsement of Ethical Leadership* . 345–359.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-005-3242-1>
- Slankis, E. (2006). Sustainable thinking, sustainable leadership-the new EQ. *Leadership* .
- Suriyankietkaew, S. (2019a). Sustainable leadership and entrepreneurship for corporate sustainability in small enterprises: An empirical analysis. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development* , 15 (1–2), 256–275.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/WREMSD.2019.098463>
- Suriyankietkaew, S. (2019b). Sustainable leadership and entrepreneurship for corporate sustainability in small enterprises: An empirical analysis. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development* , 15 (1–2), 256–275.
- Suriyankietkaew, S., & Avery, G. (2016). Sustainable leadership practices driving financial performance: Empirical evidence from Thai SMEs. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* , 8 (4), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8040327>
- Suriyankietkaew, S., & Avery, G. C. (2014). Leadership practices influencing stakeholder satisfaction in Thai SMEs. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration* , 6 (3), 247–261. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJBA-01-2014-0010>
- Suriyankietkaew, S., Krittayarungroj, K., & Iamsawan, N. (2022). Sustainable Leadership Practices and Competencies of SMEs for Sustainability and Resilience: A Community-Based Social Enterprise Study. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* , 14 (10), 1–36.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105762>
- Suriyankietkaew, S., & Petison, P. (2020). A retrospective and foresight: Bibliometric review of international research on strategic management for sustainability, 1991-2019. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* , 12 (1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12010091>
- Treviño, L. K., Brown, M., & Hartman, L. P. (2003). *Human Relations* .
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726703056001448>
- Visser, W., & Courtice, P. (2011). Sustainability leadership: Linking theory and practice. *Available at SSRN 1947221* .